

R Code

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library(lawstat)
library(perm)
library(brunnermunzel)
library(MKinfer)
library(BiocManager)
library(qvalue)
library(BonEV)
library(dplyr)
library(parallel)
library(mcreplicate)
library(future.apply)
library(readr)
library(data.table)
big<-function(num){
  avgsd2<-function(nx,meanx,sdx, ny,meany,sdy){
    x<-rnorm(n=nx,mean=meanx,sd=sdx)
    y<-rnorm(n=ny,mean=meany,sd=sdy)
    wtest <- t.test(x, y)
    wtest_perm <- perm.t.test(x,y)
    BM_Perm <- brunnermunzel.permutation.test(x,y,force = TRUE)

    BM <- brunnermunzel.test(x,y)

    out_p1 <- list(p_w = wtest$p.value, p_w_perm = wtest_perm$perm.p.value, p_BM_Perm =
    BM_Perm$p.value, p_BM = BM$p.value, id = 1)
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return(out_p1)
}
num.rep<-950
df1<-replicate(num.rep, avgsd2(nx=6,meanx=8,sdx=2, ny=10,meany=8,sdy=2))
avgsd3<-function(nx,meanx,sdx, ny,meany,sdy){
x<-rnorm(n=nx,mean=meanx,sd=sdx)
y<-rnorm(n=ny,mean=meany,sd=sdy)
wtest <- t.test(x, y)
wtest_perm <- perm.t.test(x,y)
BM_Perm <- brunnermunzel.permutation.test(x,y,force = TRUE)
BM <- brunnermunzel.test(x,y)
out_p2 <- list(p_w = wtest$p.value, p_w_perm = wtest_perm$perm.p.value, p_BM_Perm =
BM_Perm$p.value, p_BM = BM$p.value, id = 0)
return(out_p2)
}
num.rep<-50
df2<-replicate(num.rep, avgsd3(nx=6,meanx=8,sdx=2, ny=10,meany=12,sdy=2))
out_pd<-list(cbind(df1,df2))
out_t <- as.data.frame(out_pd)

out_pdtu <- sapply(out_t, unlist)
out_pv <- t(out_pdtu)
out_pvd <- as.data.frame(out_pv)
#outputting p_w with id
data_pw <-subset(out_pvd, select = - c(p_w_perm, p_BM_Perm, p_BM))
data_pw <- data_pw[order(data_pw$p_w),]

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data_pw$id_w <- data_pw$id
#outputting p_w_perm with id
data_pw_perm <-subset(out_pvd, select = - c(p_w, p_BM_Perm, p_BM))
data_pw_perm <- data_pw_perm[order(data_pw_perm$p_w_perm),]
data_pw$id_pw <- data_pw_perm$id
#outputting p_BM_Perm with id
data_BM_perm <-subset(out_pvd, select = - c(p_w, p_w_perm, p_BM))
data_BM_perm <- data_BM_perm[order(data_BM_perm$p_BM_Perm),]
data_pw$id_pBM <- data_BM_perm$id
#outputting p_BM with id
data_BM <-subset(out_pvd, select = - c(p_w, p_w_perm, p_BM_Perm))
data_BM <- data_BM[order(data_BM$p_BM),]
data_pw$id_BM <- data_BM$id
#Benjamini-Hochberg for All FOUR

data_pw$p_w_BH <- p.adjust(data_pw$p_w, "BH")
data_pw$p_w_perm_BH <- p.adjust(data_pw_perm$p_w_perm, "BH")
data_pw$p_BM_Perm_BH <- p.adjust(data_BM_perm$p_BM_Perm, "BH")
data_pw$p_BM_BH <- p.adjust(data_BM$p_BM, "BH")
#qvalues for p_w
qobj_pw = qvalue(data_pw$p_w)
data_pw$q_pw = qobj_pw$qv
qobj_pw_perm = qvalue(data_pw_perm$p_w_perm)
data_pw$q_pw_perm = qobj_pw_perm$qv
qobj_BM_perm = qvalue(data_BM_perm$p_BM_Perm)
data_pw$q_BM_perm = qobj_BM_perm$qv

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qobj_BM = qvalue(data_BM$p_BM)
data_pw$q_BM = qobj_BM$qv
summary(qobj_pw)
plot(qobj_pw)
hist(qobj_pw)
#BON-EV procedure
adjp = Bon_EV(data_pw$p_w, 0.05)
data_pw$BEV_w = adjp$raw_P_value
data_pw$BEV_w_BH = adjp$BH_adjp
data_pw$BEV_w_Storey = adjp$Storey_adjp

data_pw$BEV_w_BON = adjp$Bon_EV_adjp
adjp_pw_perm = Bon_EV(data_pw_perm$p_w_perm, 0.05)
data_pw$BEV_pw = adjp_pw_perm$raw_P_value
data_pw$BEV_pw_BH = adjp_pw_perm$BH_adjp
data_pw$BEV_pw_Storey = adjp_pw_perm$Storey_adjp
data_pw$BEV_pw_BON = adjp_pw_perm$Bon_EV_adjp
adjp_BM_perm = Bon_EV(data_BM_perm$p_BM_Perm, 0.05)
data_pw$BEV_pBM = adjp_BM_perm$raw_P_value
data_pw$BEV_pBM_BH = adjp_BM_perm$BH_adjp
data_pw$BEV_pBM_Storey = adjp_BM_perm$Storey_adjp
data_pw$BEV_pBM_BON = adjp_BM_perm$Bon_EV_adjp
adjp_BM = Bon_EV(data_BM$p_BM, 0.05)
data_pw$BEV_BM = adjp_BM$raw_P_value
data_pw$BEV_BM_BH = adjp_BM$BH_adjp
data_pw$BEV_BM_Storey = adjp_BM$Storey_adjp
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data_pw$BEV_BM_BON = adjp_BM$Bon_EV_adjp
plot(data_pw$BEV_pw, data_pw$BEV_pw_BH, type="o", col="blue", pch="o", ylab="y",
lty=1)

points(data_pw$BEV_pw, data_pw$BEV_pw_Storey, col="red", pch="*")
lines(data_pw$BEV_pw, data_pw$BEV_pw_Storey, col="red",lty=2)
points(data_pw$BEV_pw, data_pw$BEV_pw_BON, col="black", pch="+")
lines(data_pw$BEV_pw, data_pw$BEV_pw_BON, col="black",lty=3)

#Calculating FDR
data_pw$fdr_w_BH= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_w_BH <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_w_Storey= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_w_Storey <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_w_BON= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_w_BON <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pw_BH= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pw_BH <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pw_Storey= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pw_Storey <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pw_BON= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pw_BON <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pBM_BH= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pBM_BH <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pBM_Storey= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pBM_Storey <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_pBM_BON= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_pBM_BON <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_BM_BH= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_BM_BH <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_BM_Storey= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_BM_Storey <.05, 1,0)
data_pw$fdr_BM_BON= ifelse(data_pw$BEV_BM_BON <.05, 1,0) 40

gene <- 1000

#calculating proportion Welch's Test
fmean_w_BH <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_w_BH) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_w_BH = mean(id_w),tot_fdr=sum(id_w))

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fdr_outw_BH <- fmean_w_BH[2,3]
Rfdr_outw_BH <- fmean_w_BH[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outw_BH <- 1-fmean_w_BH[1,3]
fmean_w_Storey <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_w_Storey) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_w_Storey = mean(id_w),tot_fdr=sum(id_w))
fdr_outw_Storey <- fmean_w_Storey[2,3]
Rfdr_outw_Storey <- fmean_w_Storey[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outw_Storey <- 1-fmean_w_Storey[1,3]
fmean_w_BON <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_w_BON) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_w_BON = mean(id_w),tot_fdr=sum(id_w))
fdr_outw_BON <- fmean_w_BON[2,3]
Rfdr_outw_BON <- fmean_w_BON[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outw_BON <- 1-fmean_w_BON[1,3]
#calculating proportion PERM_Welch's Test
fmean_pw_BH <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pw_BH) %>%

summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pw_BH = mean(id_pw),tot_fdr=sum(id_pw))
fdr_outpw_BH <- fmean_pw_BH[2,3]
Rfdr_outpw_BH <- fmean_pw_BH[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpw_BH <- 1-fmean_pw_BH[1,3]
fmean_pw_Storey <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pw_Storey) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pw_Storey = mean(id_pw),tot_fdr=sum(id_pw))
fdr_outpw_Storey <- fmean_pw_Storey[2,3]
Rfdr_outpw_Storey <- fmean_pw_Storey[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpw_Storey <- 1-fmean_pw_Storey[1,3]
fmean_pw_BON <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pw_BON) %>%

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summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pw_BON = mean(id_pw),tot_fdr=sum(id_pw))
fdr_outpw_BON <- fmean_pw_BON[2,3]
Rfdr_outpw_BON <- fmean_pw_BON[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpw_BON <- 1-fmean_pw_BON[1,3]
#calculating proportion PERM_BM Test
fmean_pBM_BH <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pBM_BH) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pBM_BH = mean(id_pBM),tot_fdr=sum(id_pBM))
fdr_outpBM_BH <- fmean_pBM_BH[2,3]
Rfdr_outpBM_BH <- fmean_pBM_BH[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpBM_BH <- 1-fmean_pBM_BH[1,3]

fmean_pBM_Storey <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pBM_Storey) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pBM_Storey = mean(id_pBM),tot_fdr=sum(id_pBM))
fdr_outpBM_Storey <- fmean_pBM_Storey[2,3]
Rfdr_outpBM_Storey <- fmean_pBM_Storey[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpBM_Storey <- 1-fmean_pBM_Storey[1,3]
fmean_pBM_BON <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_pBM_BON) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_pBM_BON = mean(id_pBM),tot_fdr=sum(id_pBM))
fdr_outpBM_BON <- fmean_pBM_BON[2,3]
Rfdr_outpBM_BON <- fmean_pBM_BON[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outpBM_BON <- 1-fmean_pBM_BON[1,3]
#calculating proportion BM Test
fmean_BM_BH <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_BM_BH) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_BM_BH = mean(id_BM),tot_fdr=sum(id_BM))
fdr_outBM_BH <- fmean_BM_BH[2,3]
Rfdr_outBM_BH <- fmean_BM_BH[2,2]/gene

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FNDR_outBM_BH <- 1-fmean_BM_BH[1,3]
fmean_BM_Storey <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_BM_Storey) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_BM_Storey = mean(id_BM),tot_fdr=sum(id_BM))
fdr_outBM_Storey <- fmean_BM_Storey[2,3]
Rfdr_outBM_Storey <- fmean_BM_Storey[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outBM_Storey <- 1-fmean_BM_Storey[1,3]

fmean_BM_BON <- data_pw %>% group_by(fdr_BM_BON) %>%
summarise(count_fdr=n(), mean_fdr_BM_BON = mean(id_BM),tot_fdr=sum(id_BM))
fdr_outBM_BON <- fmean_BM_BON[2,3]
Rfdr_outBM_BON <- fmean_BM_BON[2,2]/gene
FNDR_outBM_BON <- 1-fmean_BM_BON[1,3]

out_final_w <- list(outw_BH=fdr_outw_BH$mean_fdr_w_BH,
outw_Storey=fdr_outw_Storey$mean_fdr_w_Storey,
outw_BON=fdr_outw_BON$mean_fdr_w_BON)

Rout_final_w <- list(Routw_BH=Rfdr_outw_BH$count_fdr,
Routw_Storey=Rfdr_outw_Storey$count_fdr, Routw_BON=Rfdr_outw_BON$count_fdr)

Nout_final_w <- list(Noutw_BH=FNDR_outw_BH$mean_fdr_w_BH,
Noutw_Storey=FNDR_outw_Storey$mean_fdr_w_Storey,
Noutw_BON=FNDR_outw_BON$mean_fdr_w_BON)

out_final_pw <- list(outpw_BH=fdr_outpw_BH$mean_fdr_pw_BH,
outpw_Storey=fdr_outpw_Storey$mean_fdr_pw_Storey,
outpw_BON=fdr_outpw_BON$mean_fdr_pw_BON)

Rout_final_pw <- list(Routpw_BH=Rfdr_outpw_BH$count_fdr,
Routpw_Storey=Rfdr_outpw_Storey$count_fdr,
Routpw_BON=Rfdr_outpw_BON$count_fdr)

Nout_final_pw <- list(Noutpw_BH=FNDR_outpw_BH$mean_fdr_pw_BH,
Noutpw_Storey=FNDR_outpw_Storey$mean_fdr_pw_Storey,
Noutpw_BON=FNDR_outpw_BON$mean_fdr_pw_BON)

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out_final_pBM <- list(outpBM_BH=fdr_outpBM_BH$mean_fdr_pBM_BH,
outpBM_Storey=fdr_outpBM_Storey$mean_fdr_pBM_Storey,
outpBM_BON=fdr_outpBM_BON$mean_fdr_pBM_BON)

Rout_final_pBM <- list(RoutpBM_BH=Rfdr_outpBM_BH$count_fdr,
RoutpBM_Storey=Rfdr_outpBM_Storey$count_fdr,
RoutpBM_BON=Rfdr_outpBM_BON$count_fdr)

Nout_final_pBM <- list(NoutpBM_BH=FNDR_outpBM_BH$mean_fdr_pBM_BH,
NoutpBM_Storey=FNDR_outpBM_Storey$mean_fdr_pBM_Storey,
NoutpBM_BON=FNDR_outpBM_BON$mean_fdr_pBM_BON)

out_final_BM <- list(outBM_BH=fdr_outBM_BH$mean_fdr_BM_BH,
outBM_Storey=fdr_outBM_Storey$mean_fdr_BM_Storey,
outBM_BON=fdr_outBM_BON$mean_fdr_BM_BON)

Rout_final_BM <- list(RoutBM_BH=Rfdr_outBM_BH$count_fdr,
RoutBM_Storey=Rfdr_outBM_Storey$count_fdr,
RoutBM_BON=Rfdr_outBM_BON$count_fdr)

Nout_final_BM <- list(NoutBM_BH=FNDR_outBM_BH$mean_fdr_BM_BH,
NoutBM_Storey=FNDR_outBM_Storey$mean_fdr_BM_Storey,
NoutBM_BON=FNDR_outBM_BON$mean_fdr_BM_BON)

out_final <-
c(Rout_final_w,out_final_w,Nout_final_w,Rout_final_pw,out_final_pw,Nout_final_pw,Rout_f
inal_pBM,out_final_pBM,Nout_final_pBM,Rout_final_BM,out_final_BM,Nout_final_BM)

return(out_final)

}

plan(multisession,workers=8)

attempt<-future_replicate(500,big(1))

out_f<-t(attempt)

out_final1 <- as.data.frame(out_f)

out_final2 <- sapply(out_final1, unlist)

colMeans(out_final2)

print(nrow(out_final2))

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